

Isotope Substitution and Polytype Control for Point Defects Identification: The Case of the Ultraviolet Color Center in Hexagonal Boron Nitride

J. Plo¹, A. Pershin^{2,3}, S. Li², T. Poirier⁴, E. Janzen⁴, H. Schutte⁴, M. Tian⁵, M. Wynn⁶, S. Bernard⁶, A. Rousseau¹, A. Ibanez¹, P. Valvin¹, W. Desrat¹, T. Michel¹, V. Jacques¹, B. Gil¹, A. Kaminska^{7,8,9}, N. Wan⁵, J. H. Edgar⁴, A. Gali^{2,3,10,*} and G. Cassabois^{1,11,†}

¹Laboratoire Charles Coulomb UMR 5221 CNRS-Université de Montpellier, 34095 Montpellier, France

²HUN-REN Wigner Research Centre for Physics, P.O. Box 49, H-1525 Budapest, Hungary

³Department of Atomic Physics, Institute of Physics, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Műgyetem rakpart 3, H-1111 Budapest, Hungary

⁴Tim Taylor Department of Chemical Engineering, Kansas State University, Manhattan, Kansas 66506, USA

⁵Key Laboratory of MEMS of Ministry of Education, School of Integrated Circuit, Southeast University, People's Republic of China

⁶IRCER, CNRS, Université Limoges, 87068 Limoges, France

⁷Institute of Physics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Aleja Lotnikow 32/46, PL-02-668, Warsaw, Poland

⁸Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, School of Exact Sciences, Dewajtis 5, 01-815 Warsaw, Poland

⁹Institute of High Pressure Physics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Sokolowska 29/37, 01-142 Warsaw, Poland

¹⁰MTA-WFK Lendület "Momentum" Semiconductor Nanostructures Research Group, P.O. Box 49, H-1525 Budapest, Hungary

¹¹Institut Universitaire de France, 75231 Paris, France

 (Received 28 June 2024; revised 22 January 2025; accepted 10 April 2025; published 8 May 2025)

Defects in crystals can have a transformative effect on the properties and functionalities of solid-state systems. Dopants in semiconductors are core components in electronic and optoelectronic devices. The control of single color centers is at the basis of advanced applications for quantum technologies. Unintentional defects can also be detrimental to the crystalline structure and hinder the development of novel materials. Whatever the research perspective, the identification of defects is a key, but complicated, and often long-standing issue. Here, we present a general methodology to identify point defects by combining isotope substitution and polytype control, with a systematic comparison between experiments and first-principles calculations. We apply this methodology to hexagonal boron nitride (*h*-BN) and its ubiquitous color center emitting in the ultraviolet spectral range. From isotopic purification of the host *h*-BN matrix, a local vibrational mode of the defect is uncovered, and isotope-selective carbon doping proves that this mode belongs to a carbon-based center. Then, by varying the stacking sequence of the host *h*-BN matrix, we unveil different optical responses to hydrostatic pressure for the nonequivalent configurations of this ultraviolet color center. We conclude that this defect is a carbon dimer in the honeycomb lattice of *h*-BN. Our results show that tuning the stacking sequence in different polytypes of a given crystal provides unique fingerprints contributing to the identification of defects in 2D materials.

DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevX.15.021045

Subject Areas: Condensed Matter Physics,
Semiconductor Physics

I. INTRODUCTION

Identifying defects is an important goal in condensed matter physics. Once the natures of extrinsic and intrinsic defects are determined, processes to improve the quality and the purity of crystals can be optimized. Conversely, the controlled incorporation of dopants either during or after the crystal growth is a basic tool for fabricating electronic and optoelectronic devices. These routine strategies of the semiconductor industry are currently being revisited to

*Contact author: gali.adam@wigner.hun-ren.hu

†Contact author: guillaume.cassabois@umontpellier.fr

Published by the American Physical Society under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license. Further distribution of this work must maintain attribution to the author(s) and the published article's title, journal citation, and DOI.

develop quantum technologies and reach the ultimate regime of single-defect creation and manipulation for advanced applications [1]. Still, identifying defects is notoriously difficult, requiring the accumulation of complementary measurements. Even for silicon, where decades of research on defects of this flagship material were reviewed by Davies in Ref. [2] in the late 1980s, only recently has the nature of some common color centers been elucidated [3,4].

The advent of graphene and the flourishing of a large variety of 2D materials motivate a new wave of research on point defects. The novel properties and functionalities of atomically thin crystals and their van der Waals heterostructures offer a new playground in solid-state physics, with a plethora of unknown defects to identify, control, and manipulate in the perspective of classical and quantum applications [5–8]. Although the recent advances in *ab initio* calculations are a key addition for screening possible candidates [9], resolving the microscopic structure of defects remains challenging.

Here, we demonstrate a general methodology to identify point defects by combining isotope substitution and polytype control, with a systematic comparison between experiments and first-principles calculations. While isotope substitution is an established resource in semiconductor physics [10], tuning the stacking sequence in different polytypes of a given crystal makes use of a crucial degree of freedom, providing unique fingerprints to help identify defects in 2D materials. We apply this methodology to hexagonal boron nitride (*h*-BN) and its ubiquitous color center emitting in the ultraviolet spectral range, to resolve the long-standing question of its nature.

h-BN is a prototypical layered material [11], with a simple honeycomb lattice of its basal plane where the orbitals of boron and nitrogen atoms are sp^2 -hybridized with a strong in-plane covalent binding. In 2004, the synthesis of high-quality crystals triggered the rise of *h*-BN in 2D materials research [12], but long before the pioneering work from NIMS-Japan, the existence of defects emitting at wavelengths of approximately 300 nm (energy approximately 4 eV) was reported [13]. Today, there is a large corpus of experimental and theoretical studies dealing with this ultraviolet color center, the so-called “4 eV defect” [13–37]; however, there is no consensus on its microscopic structure. On the one hand, Taniguchi and Watanabe [15] showed that the emission of the 4 eV defect is strongly enhanced in carbon-doped *h*-BN, suggesting that this color center may contain carbon atoms. Recent *ab initio* calculations [29–31,34–36] proposed various carbon-based centers. On the other hand, Tsushima, Tsujimura, and Uchino [20] found no correlation between the intensity of the photoluminescence (PL) signal of the 4 eV defect and the carbon concentration in *h*-BN, with possible carbon-free candidates such as the Stone-Wales defect, which is predicted to also emit at approximately 4 eV [33].

FIG. 1. Top: photoluminescence spectrum of the ultraviolet color center in *h*-BN, the so-called 4 eV defect, at low temperature (8 K). Bottom: the four most probable structures identified in the literature are the carbon dimer (C2), the carbon tetramer (C4), the carbon 6-ring (C6), and the Stone-Wales defect (SW), which is an intrinsic defect consisting of two heptagons and two pentagons made from four adjacent hexagons.

The four most probable structures proposed so far for the 4 eV defect are the carbon dimer (C2), the carbon tetramer (C4), the carbon 6-ring (C6), and the Stone-Wales defect (SW), as depicted in Fig. 1 together with the typical PL spectrum detected in *h*-BN in the corresponding spectral range (see Appendix A for experimental details). At low temperature, the emission spectrum of the 4 eV defect is dominated by a sharp line at approximately 4.09 eV, which is the zero-phonon line (ZPL) of this color center, i.e., the direct recombination without any net energy transfer with the phonon bath. At lower energy, the PL spectrum consists of a vibronic band composed of all phonon-assisted recombination channels in the defect.

By employing our methodology combining isotope substitution and polytype control, we present experimental and theoretical results that tackle the long-standing issue of

the 4 eV defect structure. We first implement isotopic purification of the host h -BN matrix (Sec. II), and we demonstrate that the phonon replica at approximately 200 meV stems from a local vibrational mode (LVM) of the center, which is not consistent with the Stone-Wales structure. Then, we perform isotope-selective carbon doping of h -BN and compare h -BN doped with the ^{12}C and ^{13}C isotopes (Sec. III), and we resolve a 6 meV isotopic shift of this LVM, unambiguously showing that the 4 eV defect is a carbon-based center. Then, we vary the stacking sequence of the host h -BN matrix, and we perform pressure-dependent PL measurements of the 4 eV defect in two h -BN polytypes (Sec. IV), either in the standard AA' stacking or in the AB one, i.e., the Bernal form of h -BN. From the different pressure-induced redshifts of the ZPL in the two h -BN polytypes, we conclude that the 4 eV defect is a carbon dimer in the h -BN honeycomb lattice.

II. ISOTOPIC PURIFICATION OF THE HOST h -BN MATRIX

We first examine the impact of the isotopic purification of the host h -BN matrix (^{10}B vs ^{11}B and ^{14}N vs ^{15}N) in samples fabricated in two facilities, following two variants of the same growth method.

A. Samples

Samples from SouthEast University (SEU series) were grown by using the metal flux method (see Appendix A 1). For boron isotope controlled single crystal growth, powders of ^{10}B (85 at%) or ^{11}B (99 at%) were used as source materials for the synthesis of ^{10}B -enriched h -BN or h - $^{11}\text{B}^{14}\text{N}$ crystals, respectively. Carbon powder (with naturally abundant isotopes, i.e., 99% ^{12}C and 1% ^{13}C) was included in all growths to promote the h -BN single crystal formation [38]. Following the characterization of h -BN crystals with a controlled composition in ^{10}B and ^{11}B and naturally abundant nitrogen [39,40], the boron isotope content of SEU1 and SEU3 was checked by Raman and UV-C PL spectroscopy measurements.

The h -BN crystals from Kansas State University (KSU series) were synthesized through the metal flux growth method described in Ref. [41]. The source materials are (i) boron powders isotopically enriched with either ^{10}B (99.2%) or ^{11}B (99.4%) and (ii) a nitrogen gas either featuring a natural ^{14}N content or enriched with the ^{15}N (>99%) isotope. Raman and UV-C PL spectroscopy have recently confirmed that such a growth method provides high-quality h -BN crystals in the four different configurations of the stable boron and nitrogen isotopes, namely, h - $^{10}\text{B}^{14}\text{N}$, h - $^{10}\text{B}^{15}\text{N}$, h - $^{11}\text{B}^{14}\text{N}$, and h - $^{11}\text{B}^{15}\text{N}$ [41].

The isotope compositions of the eight samples studied in Sec. II are summarized in Table I. SEU2 and KSU3 are reference samples grown with naturally abundant boron

TABLE I. Isotopic content of h -BN crystals fabricated at SouthEast University (SEU series) and Kansas State University (KSU series). SEU2 and KSU3 are h - ^{nat}BN crystals grown with naturally abundant boron and nitrogen isotopes. All samples in the SEU and KSU series correspond to h -BN in the AA' stacking.

	Boron		Nitrogen	
	^{10}B	^{11}B	^{14}N	^{15}N
SEU1	85	15	99.6	0.4
SEU2	19.9	80.1	99.6	0.4
SEU3	<1	>99	99.6	0.4
KSU1	99.2	0.8	99.6	0.4
KSU2	99.2	0.8	<1	>99
KSU3	19.9	80.1	99.6	0.4
KSU4	0.6	99.4	99.6	0.4
KSU5	0.6	99.4	<1	>99

and nitrogen isotopes. All samples in the SEU and KSU series correspond to h -BN in the standard AA' stacking.

B. Experimental results

Figure 2 displays the PL spectra measured in h -BN crystals of the SEU series, with the experimental setup described in Appendix A 2 a. The vibronic band of the 4 eV defect involves low-energy acoustic phonons at energies of approximately 4.08–4.09 eV close to the ZPL and also phonons spanning the full band structure as witnessed by the phonon-photon mapping in the vibronic band in this color center [19]. We define δ as the energy splitting between the ZPL at approximately 4.1 eV and the phonon replica at approximately 3.945 eV, and Δ as the one with the replica at approximately 3.9 eV (Fig. 2). The phonon replica at approximately 3.9 eV has so far been assigned to the recombination assisted by the emission of a $\text{LO}_3(\Gamma)$ optical phonon at the center of the Brillouin zone [19,42], because the energy splitting Δ with the ZPL matches the $\text{LO}_3(\Gamma)$ phonon energy. We see below that our measurements in isotopically purified h -BN crystals rebut this initial interpretation. In what follows, we focus on the isotopic shifts of the ZPL energy and of the Δ and δ splittings.

In the full-scale display of the SEU series in Fig. 2, the PL spectra of the 4 eV defect in isotopically purified h -BN crystals appear very similar. There are, however, some discernible differences for the narrowest lines. First, the ZPL and the phonon replica at approximately 3.9 eV have widths that change from one sample to another. Because the latter belongs to the satellite-vibronic band of the former, the broader the ZPL, the larger the width of the phonon replica, as seen in the temperature-dependent measurements in Ref. [19]. Here, the ZPL width is 2, 1.6, and 2.2 meV from SEU1 to SEU3, while the phonon replica at approximately 3.9 eV monotonically narrows with a width of 5.6, 3.2, and 3 meV, respectively. We, thus, conclude that

FIG. 2. PL spectra in the UV-B, at 8 K, recorded in isotopically purified h -BN samples from the SEU series (see detailed isotopic composition in Table I). PL excitation energy = 6.32 eV. Δ is the energy splitting between the zero-phonon line at approximately 4.1 eV and the phonon replica at approximately 3.9 eV, and δ the splitting with the phonon replica at approximately 3.945 eV.

the width variations of the phonon replica are not related to the inhomogeneous broadening of the ZPL, pointing to an isotopic effect. Second, the ZPL and phonon replica shift within the SEU series (Fig. 2). Albeit hardly observable in Fig. 2, there is a redshift of the lines for light isotopes [see quantitative estimates below, Fig. 4(a)].

This systematic effect of the isotopic purification is better resolved for the KSU series in Fig. 3. In Fig. 3, we present the PL spectra of the KSU series (Table I), with the four configurations of the stable boron and nitrogen isotopes, h - $^{10}\text{B}^{14}\text{N}$, h - $^{10}\text{B}^{15}\text{N}$, h - $^{11}\text{B}^{14}\text{N}$, and h - $^{11}\text{B}^{15}\text{N}$, together with a reference h - $^{\text{Nat}}\text{BN}$ sample (KSU3). In contrast to the SEU series, no carbon was intentionally added during the crystal growth, leading to a weaker PL signal at approximately 4 eV, in agreement with previous reports [15]. The 4 eV defect emission is dim in the KSU series because of the high purity of the boron and nitrogen precursors employed for the growth of isotopically purified h -BN. This point is of great importance in the prospect of the isotope-selective carbon doping, as later discussed in Sec. III. Because of the sparse emission, recording the PL spectrum of the 4 eV defect required the use of micro-PL measurements (see Appendix A 2 a), to locate the areas of highest defects density in crystals of the KSU series, hence the reduced signal-to-noise ratio in Fig. 3 compared to Fig. 2. To better observe the isotopic shifts of the ZPL and phonon replica, we use a split x -axis representation in Fig. 3, where we enlarge around two intervals of the same 13 meV extension, centered at 3.8975 and 4.0975 eV. There, both the ZPL and the phonon replica systematically redshift as a function of the isotopic masses. Interestingly,

the ZPL energy changes only by approximately 3 meV in contrast to approximately 5 meV for the phonon replica, thus revealing the dependence of the energy splitting Δ (as defined in Fig. 2) with the isotopic composition. Similar to the SEU series, the phonon replica is the broadest for the lightest isotopes (h - $^{10}\text{B}^{14}\text{N}$, KSU1), further supporting the evidence of an isotopic effect.

FIG. 3. PL spectra in the UV-B, at 8 K, recorded in isotopically purified h -BN samples from the KSU series (see detailed isotopic composition in Table I), enlarged around the phonon replica at approximately 3.9 eV and the zero-phonon line at approximately 4.1 eV. PL excitation energy = 6.32 eV.

In Fig. 4(a), we merge the data of the SEU and KSU series for the isotopic shift of the ZPL. For each series, we subtract the ZPL energy measured in the reference h - ^{nat}BN sample (4.0988 eV for SEU2 and 4.0982 eV for KSU3) from the value found in the different isotopically purified h -BN crystals. We follow this procedure because the two series were measured in different runs. The 0.6 meV difference between SEU2 and KSU3 lies within our absolute calibration accuracy, thus showing the repeatability of the 4 eV defect formation in h -BN crystals, not only grown at different growth facilities, but also with different procedures where the carbon quantity significantly varies.

Following Ref. [40], we plot the isotopic shift of the ZPL as a function of the reduced mass μ , expressed in units of the atomic mass as

$$\frac{1}{\mu} = \frac{1}{10x + 11(1-x)} + \frac{1}{14y + 15(1-y)}, \quad (1)$$

where x and y are the ^{10}B and ^{14}N mole fractions of the boron and nitrogen isotopes, respectively. The isotopic shifts measured for the SEU (empty squares) and KSU (full circles) h -BN crystals assemble on the same line in Fig. 4(a), demonstrating the universal impact of isotopic purification of the host h -BN matrix on the ZPL of the 4 eV defect. We compare these data to the isotopic shift of the h -BN band gap [dashed line in Fig. 4(a)], which is due, at low temperatures, to the zero-point vibrations mediated by the electron-phonon coupling [10]. It was first estimated in h -BN in Ref. [40] and more recently in Ref. [41] with the extension of isotopic purification to ^{15}N . The approximately

3 meV shift of the 4 eV defect ZPL appears to be 3 times smaller than the h -BN band gap shift, over the investigated range of isotopic masses. Such a discrepancy is the signature of the electronic localization in a deep level, interpreted below with our first-principles calculations.

Figure 4(b) displays the merged data of the SEU and KSU series for the energy splitting Δ , as defined in Fig. 2, as a function of the reduced mass μ . Similarly to the ZPL isotopic shift in Fig. 4(a), the congruent measurements in samples fabricated in two different growth facilities reveal the impact of the isotope control in h -BN on the energy splitting Δ . Because Δ corresponds to a characteristic vibrational energy in phonon-assisted recombination processes, its variation with the isotopic masses is straightforward, in contrast to the ZPL isotopic shift which stems from more subtle effects related to the electron-phonon coupling and the zero-point vibrations. Specifically, Δ decreases with the reduced mass μ [Fig. 4(b)], because the frequency of an harmonic oscillator is inversely proportional to the square root of its mass, as observed by Raman spectroscopy in h -BN in Refs. [40,41]. Because Δ is of the order of 200 meV, we compare its isotopic shift to the one of the $\text{LO}_3(\Gamma)$ optical phonon at the center of the Brillouin zone. In Fig. 4(b), calculations of the $\text{LO}_3(\Gamma)$ energy within the QUANTUMESPRESSO package are displayed as a dashed line, while the experimental values measured in Ref. [43] correspond to the stars. Strikingly, in h - ^{nat}BN ($\mu = 6.1$), the energy splitting Δ almost coincides with the $\text{LO}_3(\Gamma)$ energy. This is why the phonon replica at approximately 3.9 eV was initially interpreted as involving the emission of one $\text{LO}_3(\Gamma)$ phonon [19]. However, varying the isotopic

FIG. 4. (a) Isotopic shift of the zero-phonon line at approximately 4.1 eV with respect to h - ^{nat}BN crystals, grown with naturally abundant boron and nitrogen isotopes, as a function of the reduced mass μ in units of the atomic mass (amu). The dashed line corresponds to the experimental isotopic shift of the h -BN band gap at approximately 5.95 eV, from Ref. [41]. (b) Isotopic shift of the energy splitting Δ , between the zero-phonon line at approximately 4.1 eV and the phonon replica at approximately 3.9 eV (as defined in Fig. 2), as a function of the reduced mass μ . The dashed line corresponds to the calculated isotopic shift of the $\text{LO}_3(\Gamma)$ optical phonon at the center of the Brillouin zone, and stars indicate the experimental values, from Ref. [43]. (c) Isotopic shift of the energy splitting δ , between the zero-phonon line at approximately 4.1 eV and the phonon replica at approximately 3.945 eV (as defined in Fig. 2), as a function of the reduced mass μ . The dashed line corresponds to the calculated isotopic shift of the $\text{LO}_{2/3}(K)$ optical phonon at the K point of the Brillouin zone. In all panels, experimental data are displayed as empty squares for the SEU series, and full circles for the KSU one, with the same color code as Figs. 2 and 3.

composition leads to distinct variations, thus unveiling that Δ is not the energy of one $\text{LO}_3(\Gamma)$ phonon and that the phonon replica at approximately 3.9 eV stems from a LVM of the 4 eV defect.

It is instructive to compare the δ splitting, between the ZPL and the phonon replica at approximately 3.945 eV, as defined in Fig. 2. In that case, the variations of δ with the reduced mass μ nicely follow the calculated isotopic shift of the $\text{LO}_{2/3}(K)$ phonon, i.e., the longitudinal optical mode of the quasidegenerate 2 and 3 branches at the K point of the Brillouin zone [dashed line, Fig. 4(c)]. This Bloch phonon mode of the h -BN matrix gives rise to a large peak at approximately 155 meV in the phonon density states; hence, the phonon replica at approximately 3.945 eV can be attributed to recombination assisted by the emission of a $\text{LO}_{2/3}(K)$ optical phonon [19]. Our experiments in isotopically purified h -BN crystals confirm this interpretation, and we make use of this complementary fingerprint when analyzing the isotope-selective carbon doping in Sec. III.

C. *Ab initio* calculations

After presenting the first part of our experimental findings, we now turn our attention to a theoretical identification of the defect structure responsible for the isotopic response observed in the 4.1 eV PL signal. We apply highly convergent supercell plane wave density functional theory calculations to calculate the PL signals of selected defects (see Appendix A 3 for details). In Fig. 1, we illustrate the structures of four defects: the SW defect and three different complexes based on carbon impurities, all of which have previously been suggested as potential emitters of the 4.1 eV signal. Other four-carbon defects were not considered, because they exhibit a large redshift in the emission spectra relative to the carbon tetramer (C4) displayed in Fig. 1, due to the delocalization of frontier orbitals; see, for instance, Ref. [44]. Initially, due to the strong similarities in the PL spectra of the three carbon-based defects in Fig. 1, we focus on the carbon dimer (C2) for our spectral simulations, as a representative example of a defect made of an even number of carbon impurities in h -BN. The electronic structure of the carbon dimer was discussed in Refs. [30,31,34,36]. It was shown that the ZPL of the C2 defect in its neutral charge state originates from a singlet to singlet transition where an electron occupying a p_z orbital localized on the acceptorlike C_N passes to a p_z orbital of the donorlike C_B [30]. For the Stone-Wales defect, the reader can refer to the analysis of Hamdi *et al.* in Ref. [33].

In Fig. 5, we show the calculated modifications to the PL spectrum of these defects with variations in the isotope composition of the host material. Our simulations reveal that the PL signal of the C2 defect closely matches our experimental findings, displaying features such as a prominent phonon replica approximately 200 meV below the

FIG. 5. Phonon sidebands, calculated for (a) C2 and (c) SW defects in h -BN of different isotope compositions. (b) Calculated isotopic shift of the ZPL at approximately 4.1 eV for the C2 and SW defects. (d) Calculated isotopic shift of the energy splitting Δ , between the zero-phonon line at approximately 4.1 eV and the phonon replica (as defined in Fig. 2) for C2 and SW defects. Naturally abundant carbon atoms (^{12}C) are considered here for the C2 defect. The isotopic variations of the ZPL energy and Δ splitting are calculated with an accuracy of approximately 1 meV.

ZPL and a shoulder at approximately 170 meV. The discrepancy in the calculated PL spectra at approximately 30–50 meV is attributed to the size of the supercell, which introduces a low-energy cutoff leading to an underestimation of the contribution of low-energy acoustic phonons to the vibronic band. Such size effects are mitigated in larger supercells [32]. In contrast, the SW defect exhibits two groups of active modes at around 210 and 150 meV. The 210 meV mode is localized at the boron and nitrogen atoms, connecting two pentagons (see Fig. 15 in Appendix B 2). The three active modes at approximately 150 meV are hybridized with the bulk modes, with a particular impact on the atoms within the nitrogen-rich pentagon. For both types of defects, the phonon sidebands are primarily influenced by stretching modes, as depicted in Figs. 15 and 17 in Appendix B 2. Additionally, the partial Huang-Rhys factors for other active modes, which account for additional peaks in our simulated vibronic bands, are also presented in Figs. 15 and 17.

Figure 5(b) further displays the calculated isotopic shift of the ZPL for the C2 defect, which increases systematically with the reduced mass μ —consistently with

our experimental observations. Conversely, a less clear trend is observed for the SW defect, which is likely due to an imbalanced participation of nitrogen and boron atoms to the optical transition [33]. Most strikingly, the vibrational energy of the stretching mode in the SW defect, involving both boron and nitrogen atoms, exhibits a pronounced decrease of approximately 9 meV with changes in the isotope composition of *h*-BN, as shown in Fig. 5(d). This shift is comparable to the one of a Bloch mode of the *h*-BN matrix, such as the $\text{LO}_3(\Gamma)$ phonon [Fig. 4(b)]. In contrast, the energy of the carbon-localized mode in C2 marginally decreases only by less than 2 meV. A direct comparison between the calculated Δ splittings and our experimental data is provided in Fig. 16 in Appendix B 2, where the three carbon-based defects (C2, C4, and C6) are considered. Notably, the computed Δ splittings for the C2 defect closely align with our experimental results, whereas for the carbon tetramer (C4), they are systematically overestimated by 4 meV, and underestimated by 2 meV for the carbon 6-ring (C6). Therefore, given the quantitative agreement between our experimental and theoretical results, we infer that the C2 defect is so far the most likely candidate for the 4.1 eV emission.

III. ISOTOPE-SELECTIVE CARBON DOPING

Having identified the phonon replica at approximately 3.9 eV as stemming from a LVM and having ruled out the Stone-Wales center (Fig. 1) as a compatible structure for the isotopic shift of this LVM, we examine in this section the impact of isotope-selective carbon doping for further testing and screening the carbon-based defects represented in Fig. 1, among which the carbon dimer appears as a suitable candidate at this stage.

A. Samples

h-BN crystals were grown at KSU by precipitating from a solution formed by dissolving either ^{10}B or ^{11}B enriched boron in molten iron. The solution was formed by heating to 1550 °C, holding at this temperature to homogenize the solution, and then slowly cooling to 1550 °C at 1 °C/h (compared to 4 °C/h in previous studies [22]). Nitrogen (250 sccm) and forming gas: argon (95%) hydrogen (5%) (50 sccm) continuously flowed over the solution during the process.

For isotope-selective carbon doping, graphite powder was added to the starting materials, either with the natural distribution of isotopes (approximately 99% ^{12}C and 1% ^{13}C) or enriched in ^{13}C (99% with 1% ^{12}C). For $^{\text{Nat}}\text{C}$ doping, graphitic carbon (99.995% purity) was loaded at a 0.44 mass ratio to that of the boron. The total composition was 96.65 mass percent iron, 2.33 mass percent natural boron, and 1.02 mass percent carbon. For isotopically enriched ^{13}C doping, isotopic carbon (97.1% chemical, 99% isotope purity) was used in lieu of the natural carbon.

The carbon doping process has been refined to be more reproducible since what was first reported in Ref. [22]. In that work, the boron source was exclusively boron nitride; in this work, elemental boron powder (99%) was used. Furthermore, in this study, carbon monoxide was not used, only forming gas to getter oxygen. Additionally, the solvent was pure iron (99.99% purity) contrary to the mixtures reported in Ref. [22]. Overall, the residual $^{\text{Nat}}\text{C}$ content relative to the boron in each sample is significantly lower than those reported by Pelini *et al.* [22]. This point was already made in Sec. II when presenting the measurements by micro-PL in the KSU series (Fig. 3). This is a major difference compared to previous studies where unintentional $^{\text{Nat}}\text{C}$ contamination presumably hindered the impact of ^{13}C doping [22], and it is the key here for revealing the fingerprints of isotope-selective carbon doping in *h*-BN.

B. Experimental results

The PL spectra recorded in $^{\text{Nat}}\text{C}:\textit{h}\text{-BN}$ and $^{13}\text{C}:\textit{h}\text{-BN}$ crystals are plotted in Fig. 6 as a function of the detuning with the ZPL energy, in order to eliminate any isotopic shift of the ZPL and solely focus on the influence of the carbon isotopes on the vibronic band spectrum. When replacing $^{\text{Nat}}\text{C}$ (i.e., ^{12}C at 99%) with ^{13}C , modifications occur in two ranges of energy detuning: (i) at approximately 200 meV, which corresponds to the LVM energy identified in Sec. II, and (ii) at approximately 400 meV, where phonon-assisted recombination involves two-phonon overtones of the 200 meV LVM. Enlarging around 200 meV detunings resolves a 6 meV blueshift of the phonon replica in $^{13}\text{C}:\textit{h}\text{-BN}$ and also a line broadening (Fig. 6, inset). Because the ZPL width hardly changes from 2.2 to 2.8 meV in $^{\text{Nat}}\text{C}:\textit{h}\text{-BN}$ and $^{13}\text{C}:\textit{h}\text{-BN}$, the latter effect does not come from an increased inhomogeneous broadening in $^{13}\text{C}:\textit{h}\text{-BN}$ crystals, thus pointing for an isotopic effect, similarly to our previous results in Sec. II dealing with the impact of the isotopic purification of the host matrix.

The blueshift of the phonon replica at approximately 3.9 eV implies a reduced energy of the LVM, which is consistent with a carbon-based color center where the heavier mass of the ^{13}C isotope with respect to $^{\text{Nat}}\text{C}$ results in vibrational modes of lower energy [45,46]. Importantly, the phonon-assisted recombination line at approximately 3.945 eV, corresponding to an energy detuning $\delta \sim 155$ meV, is not affected by the ^{13}C vs $^{\text{Nat}}\text{C}$ selective carbon doping (Fig. 6, inset). This effect is perfectly in line with our findings in Sec. II, where we conclude that the approximately 3.945 eV line originates from the recombination assisted by the emission of a Bloch phonon mode of the *h*-BN matrix. For moderate carbon concentrations, the phonon band structure of *h*-BN is unperturbed by the presence of carbon impurities, so that

FIG. 6. Impact of the isotopic substitution (^{Nat}C vs ^{13}C) on the PL spectrum of the 4 eV defect, plotted as a function of the energy detuning with the ZPL energy, in $h\text{-}^{Nat}\text{BN}$ crystals grown with naturally abundant boron and nitrogen isotopes. PL excitation energy = 6.32 eV, sample temperature = 8 K. Inset: enlargement around the local vibrational mode at approximately 200 meV. The ZPL energy is 4.0971 eV in $^{Nat}\text{C}:h\text{-BN}$ and 4.0988 eV in $^{13}\text{C}:h\text{-BN}$.

any phonon-assisted recombination line involving a delocalized vibrational mode will not be influenced by isotope-selective carbon doping.

From the reduced Δ splitting in $^{13}\text{C}:h\text{-BN}$, on the one hand, and the constant δ value, on the other hand, we unambiguously conclude that the 4 eV defect is a carbon-based defect in $h\text{-BN}$. Our results, thus, resolve the long-standing controversy on the interplay between carbon and this ultraviolet color center in $h\text{-BN}$, carbon being interpreted either as a constituent of the 4 eV defect, or only as a vector of its formation, or even as a simple bystander [13–31,33–36].

C. *Ab initio* calculations

In order to further quantitatively interpret our experimental results, we conducted first-principles calculations (see Appendix A 3) to examine the impact of carbon isotopes on the optoelectronic properties of the three carbon-based candidate structures (Fig. 1). First, we focus on analyzing the response of the carbon dimer (C2), which was identified as the most probable defect structure in Sec. II C. Figure 7 illustrates a direct comparison between our theoretical and experimental spectra. Our calculations for both $^{12}\text{C}2$ and $^{13}\text{C}2$ defects exhibit a fair agreement with our experimental data, particularly capturing the characteristic broadening of the first and second phonon replicas attributed to the ^{13}C isotope. The calculated variation of the

FIG. 7. Calculated PL spectrum of the carbon dimer (C2) for either ^{12}C (a) or ^{13}C (b) impurities. First-principles simulations (solid lines) are compared to experimental results in Fig. 6 (lines and symbols). In the present case of the carbon dimer, the calculated ZPL energies coincide with the experimental ones so that no spectral shift is applied for the comparison (unlike Fig. 18 in Appendix B, where the computed PL spectra of the C4 and C6 defects are shifted for comparing with experimental data).

Δ splitting was determined to be 6 meV, which is the exact experimental value (Fig. 6). Importantly, the calculated Δ splitting is much larger than the error bars associated with inhomogeneous broadening, which are computed to be 0.2 meV for the $^{12}\text{C}_2$ defect and 0.4 meV for the $^{13}\text{C}_2$ defect.

Notably, our analysis revealed a slight underestimation of the computed shift by approximately 2 meV, when considering only the energy of the primary stretching mode. This effect can be attributed to two additional modes at around 190 meV that are partially localized on the carbon atoms [see Fig. 17(a) in Appendix B 2], shaping the vibration peak in the phonon sideband of PL. The combined influence of these three modes explains the change in the isotope-dependent broadening of the vibration peak at around 200 meV, caused by the carbon isotopes. Interestingly, the relative contribution of the two additional modes at approximately 190 meV is also influenced by the nitrogen and boron isotopes, with a significant increase observed for the lighter atoms [see Fig. 17(b) in Appendix B 2]. This explains the systematic broadening of the band at approximately 3.9 eV for the lighter boron and nitrogen isotopes, as observed in our experiments presented in Sec. II. These findings emphasize the importance of conducting a comprehensive spectrum simulation to accurately capture the isotopic effects for defects in *h*-BN.

When examining the two other carbon defects, we observe a poorer agreement with our experimental data (see Appendix B 2, Fig. 18). Specifically, the carbon tetramer (C4) also displays a 6 meV isotopic shift of the Δ splitting, but at a higher vibrational energy, particularly evident at emission energies of approximately 3.7 eV where phonon-assisted recombination involves two-phonon overtones of the 200 meV LVM. The carbon 6-ring (C6) exhibits a larger isotopic shift of 9 meV for the Δ splitting, along with an overall greater mismatch between the energies of the active vibrational modes. These discrepancies further support our conclusion that the carbon dimer is the likely defect responsible for the observed 4.1 eV signal in *h*-BN.

IV. STACKING SEQUENCE CONTROL OF THE HOST *h*-BN MATRIX

To further screen the different carbon-based candidate structures, we now make use of a novel degree of freedom, which is the stacking sequence of the *h*-BN basal planes [47]. We investigate *h*-BN polytypes either in the standard *AA'* stacking [48] or in the *AB* one, corresponding to the Bernal form of *h*-BN [47]. By pressure-dependent PL measurements of the 4 eV defect, we demonstrate that the perturbative response to hydrostatic pressure is stacking dependent, providing additional key fingerprints for the definitive identification of the 4 eV defect as a carbon dimer.

A. Samples

AA'-stacked *h*-BN crystals were synthesized at KSU with the well-established metal flux growth method described in Ref. [22]. This method also produces *AB*-stacked *h*-BN crystals but of reduced size, few tens of micrometers (because of the polytypic nature of the currently available samples [26,49–51]), i.e., a dimension hardly appropriate for high-pressure measurements in a diamond-anvil cell (see Appendix A 2 b) with limited spatial resolution compared to confocal microscopy at ambient pressure [22,26]. Although experimental data could be obtained in such samples (see details and Fig. 14 in Appendix B 1 b), the use of an *AB*-*h*-BN powder has allowed us to explore the hydrostatic pressure response of *AB*-stacked *h*-BN [Fig. 8(b)].

The *AB*-stacked *h*-BN powder was synthesized by thermochemical conversion of a lithium-modified ammonia borane (NH_3BH_3) precursor (see Appendix A 4 a). The precursor was placed in a BN crucible in a glove box and then put in a sealed tube under argon atmosphere to avoid oxygen contamination of the samples during the transfer to the furnace. The furnace was put under vacuum (0.1 mbar, 30 min), refilled with nitrogen, and maintained under a constant flow of 200 mL/min of N_2 during the whole heat treatment. The heating and cooling ramps were $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, and the final temperature was 1800°C with a dwelling time of 2 h. The *AB* stacking was evidenced by PL spectroscopy in the UV-C and UV-B spectral domains (see Appendix B 1 a, Fig. 12), where the simultaneous observation of a line at approximately 6.035 eV and a ZPL doublet for the 4 eV defect [see Fig. 12(a) at ambient pressure and Fig. 13 under hydrostatic pressures] proves the Bernal form of BN [26,49].

B. Experimental results

Pressure-dependent measurements of the 4 eV defect emission were performed with the experimental setup described in Appendix A 2 b. All investigated samples below correspond to *h*- ^{10}B BN grown with naturally abundant boron and nitrogen isotopes.

In the case of the standard *AA'* stacking [Fig. 8(a)], the emission was studied from ambient pressure up to approximately 5 GPa. The PL spectrum smoothly redshifts when raising the hydrostatic pressure, and the ZPL width increases. At 2.5 GPa, the ZPL is too broad to be observed, but the PL emission still peaks at the ZPL energy, with a surrounding spectrum determined by the low-energy acoustic phonons sideband, similarly to temperature-dependent experiments [19]. This explains the broad PL bands at high pressures in Fig. 8, where the PL spectra, normalized to their maximum intensity, are dominated by the vibronic bands of the color center. From the pressure-dependent PL measurements in Fig. 8(a), we extract the pressure-induced redshifts of the ZPL and Δ -split phonon replica in the *AA'* stacking (Fig. 9), and we deduce a pressure

FIG. 8. Impact of the stacking sequence (AA' vs AB) of the host h -BN matrix on the pressure-dependent PL response of the 4 eV defect in h - nat BN grown with naturally abundant boron and nitrogen isotopes: host h -BN matrix in either AA' (a) or AB (b) stacking. An enlargement around 4 eV showing the ZPL doublet in AB - h -BN is shown in Fig. 13. PL excitation energy = 4.5 eV, sample temperature = 7 K. In each panel, the PL spectra are vertically shifted for clarity. Hydrostatic pressures (GPa): $\{0.04, 0.65, 1.30, 1.97, 2.50, 3.13, 3.74, 4.36, 5.03\}$ in (a) and $\{0.46, 1.60, 2.95, 3.48, 4.10, 4.76, 5.42, 5.90, 6.65, 7.15, 7.80, 8.81\}$ in (b), from bottom to top.

coefficient of -25.5 ± 0.5 meV/GPa, in agreement with previous studies [23].

Pressure-dependent experiments in AB - h -BN reveal the striking influence of the stacking sequence on the optoelectronic properties of the 4 eV defect subjected to hydrostatic pressure. From the PL spectra recorded up to approximately 9 GPa [Fig. 8(b)], the pressure-induced perturbation appears to be significantly reduced with respect to AA' - h -BN, with a redshift of only approximately 100 meV at about 9 GPa in AB - h -BN compared to approximately 125 meV at about 5 GPa in AA' - h -BN. Over the full range of investigated pressure, we estimate an average approximately threefold decrease of the pressure-induced redshift in AB - h -BN (Fig. 9).

Because of the staggered stacking of the h -BN basal planes in AB - h -BN, there are two nonequivalent configurations of the 4 eV defect, as experimentally demonstrated in Ref. [26] and schematically represented in Fig. 10. One of the two substitutional carbons has no neighbor in the adjacent planes along the c axis so that the carbon dimer is either $C_B C_N^{(B)}$ [so-called $AB1$ configuration, Fig. 10(b)] or $C_B^{(N)} C_N$ [so-called $AB2$ configuration, Fig. 10(c)], in contrast to AA' - h -BN, where the carbon dimer has only the $C_B^{(N)} C_N^{(B)}$ form [Fig. 10(a)]. This is specific to the AB stacking, and we stress that there is only one configuration of the carbon dimer (and by extension of the carbon tetramer and carbon 6-ring) for the AA' but also for the AA and ABC stackings, so that the experimental observation of a ZPL doublet at approximately 4 eV is a fingerprint

of AB - h -BN together with a PL line in the UV-C range at approximately 6.035 eV [26,49].

This specific ZPL doublet was used for characterizing the AB - h -BN powder synthesized by thermoconversion of lithium-modified ammonia borane (see Appendix B 1 a, Fig. 12). In the following, the two components of the ZPL doublet at 4.161 and 4.145 eV are labeled $AB1$ and $AB2$,

FIG. 9. Pressure-induced redshifts of the ZPL and phonon replica at approximately 3.9 eV for AA' and AB -stacked h -BN, with two nonequivalent configurations of the 4 eV defect in AB - h -BN. The slopes of linear fits to the experimental data give the pressure coefficients.

FIG. 10. Atomic configurations of the C2 defect in different stacking sequences of *h*-BN: AA' (a) and AB (b),(c) showing the two nonequivalent forms of the carbon dimer in AB-*h*-BN (as in Fig. 1, boron atoms are plotted in green and nitrogen atoms in gray). The so-called AB1 configuration corresponds to $C_B C_N^{(B)}$ (b), while the AB2 one to $C_B^{(N)} C_N$ (c). The nonequivalence is identical for the carbon tetramer and the carbon 6-ring by repetition of the atomic arrangements according to the schemes in Fig. 1. Left column: top view, along the *c* axis. Right column: side view, perpendicularly to the *c* axis.

respectively. Remarkably, our pressure-dependent PL measurements resolve different pressure-induced redshifts for the two nonequivalent configurations of the 4 eV defect. Although the AB1 ZPL energy cannot be estimated over the full range of investigated pressure but only until approximately 5 GPa (see Appendix B 1 a, Fig. 13), the pressure-induced redshifts of the AB1 and AB2 ZPLs and their Δ -split phonon replicas are different (Fig. 9), and we estimate values of -7.7 ± 0.5 and -9.7 ± 0.3 meV/GPa for AB1 and AB2, respectively. The AB-*h*-BN microcrystals were similar, with pressure coefficients of -7.4 ± 0.5 and -10.4 ± 0.4 that are identical to the data in Fig. 9 within experimental error (see Appendix B 1 b, Fig. 14).

Although the modification of the stacking sequence of the host *h*-BN matrix changes the ZPL energy of the 4 eV defect only by approximately 1% from AA' to AB, the huge variations of the perturbative response to hydrostatic pressure in the two *h*-BN polytypes reveal the importance of considering the interlayer coupling. Together with the more subtle difference in the pressure-induced redshifts of the two nonequivalent configurations of the color center in AB-*h*-BN, these experimental results provide crucial inputs for further elucidating the defect structure.

C. *Ab initio* calculations

We investigated the impact of hydrostatic pressure on the PL spectra within our theoretical framework (see Appendix A 3). The application of hydrostatic pressure results in a compressive strain, with the majority of the strain being absorbed along the *c* direction (approximately 12% compression in both AA' and AB stacking sequences at 10 GPa), while the basal plane lattice constants experience smaller variations (approximately 0.7% compression). Figure 11 illustrates the comparison of the pressure coefficients for the various carbon-based defects. Our calculations reveal that the values obtained for the carbon dimer (C2) closely match the experimental data, reaching again nearly quantitative agreement. For the carbon tetramer (C4), the relative variations of the computed pressure-induced shifts from one defect configuration to another are in agreement with our experimental findings, but the absolute values of the pressure coefficients are significantly overestimated by a factor of approximately 2 with respect to our measurements. The discrepancy with the experimental data is even more pronounced for the

FIG. 11. Pressure coefficients of the ZPL for the three configurations of the carbon-based UV-color center in AA' and AB-stacked *h*-BN: experimental data on the *x* axis vs theoretical values on the *y* axis for the C2 (full circles), C4 (empty squares), and C6 (empty pentagons) structures.

carbon 6-ring (C6), for which the *AB1* ZPL is calculated to be almost insensitive to hydrostatic pressure. For completeness, the pressure coefficients for the SW defect are -14.7 , -3.72 , and -24.4 meV/GPa in the *AA'*, *AB1*, and *AB2* configurations, respectively; furthermore, the one for the carbon dimer in rhombohedral boron nitride would be -15 meV/GPa.

To elucidate the difference of pressure effects on the C2 defect in *AA'* and *AB* stacking sequences, we have analyzed its electronic properties, shown in Table II (Appendix B 2). The primary effect of hydrostatic pressure is the compression of the interlayer spacing, leading to an increased screening effect. Consequently, this results in the stabilization of defect levels with respect to the band edges. In the case of the *AA'* sequence, both C_B and C_N are directly linked to nitrogen and boron atoms from adjacent layers, respectively [Fig. 10(a)]. Therefore, both occupied and empty levels are stabilized, resulting in a redshift of the PL signal. This effect can also be interpreted as a suppression of the exchange interaction between the donor and acceptor defects due to enhanced screening. Conversely, in the *AB* stacking configuration, only one carbon atom of the pair (C_N in *AB1* and C_B in *AB2*) interacts directly with neighboring layers. Consequently, the empty defect level in *AB1* and an occupied level in *AB2* are primarily stabilized, while their counterparts are less affected. As a consequence, the redshift of the PL signal is less pronounced compared to the *AA'* sequence. This elucidates the difference in pressure effects between *AA'* and *AB* stacking arrangements in terms of electronic response.

To further understand the difference between *AB1* and *AB2* configurations of the C2 defect, we also considered the effects of structural relaxation, with relevant data summarised in Table III (Appendix B 2). Our analysis, consistent with our previous research [32], reveals that interlayer polarization occurs as electron density leaks from the lone pairs of nitrogen to boron atoms. In the *AB2* configuration [Fig. 10(c)], where the donor carbon occupies the boron site (C_B), a strong repulsive interaction with neighboring nitrogen atoms from adjacent layers is observed in the excited state. This interaction causes the defect to slide along the symmetry axis; the degree of sliding increases under pressure, resulting in a decrease in the N-C-N angle. Consequently, this distortion leads to a large increase in the total Huang-Rhys factor for this configuration, which is also reflected in our experimental spectra. In contrast, no strong interaction between C_N^+ and adjacent boron atoms is observed, as they lack electron density. Therefore, the *AB1* and *AB2* configurations of the C2 defect show a different structural response to hydrostatic pressure, as seen in our experiments.

V. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

We have presented a general methodology for point defect identification, combining isotope substitution and

polytype control, with a systematic comparison between experiments and first-principles calculations. We have applied it to the 4 eV defect in *h*-BN and tackled the long-standing issue of the nature of this ubiquitous color center in *h*-BN. By implementing isotopic purification of the host *h*-BN matrix, followed by isotope-selective carbon doping of *h*-BN, we have reduced the number of candidate structures to a few carbon-based centers. Then, by playing with the stacking sequence of the host matrix in two *h*-BN polytypes, we have revealed different perturbative responses to hydrostatic pressure for the nonequivalent configurations of the 4 eV defect in *AA'* and *AB*-stacked *h*-BN. Our comprehensive set of experimental and theoretical results demonstrate that the 4 eV defect is a carbon dimer in the *h*-BN honeycomb lattice.

Our study is an important milestone in *h*-BN research, where the impact of carbon is the subject of an intense debate. The demonstration that the 4 eV defect is a carbon dimer sets the basis for a better understanding of the incorporation of carbon in *h*-BN and its possible role in *h*-BN dopings. The carbon dimer is an isoelectronic defect in the *h*-BN honeycomb lattice, but its dissociation may lead to the formation of donor-acceptor pairs, signatures of which have been reported in the optical response of *h*-BN [16–18,25,31]. Both *n* and *p* dopings are still in their infancy in *h*-BN [52–54], and our results may shed a new light for elucidating the striking persistent photoconductivity phenomenon reported in *h*-BN grown by metal-organic chemical vapor deposition [55]. Moreover, the identification of the carbon dimer raises the question of the optical responses of the carbon tetramer and carbon 6-ring, which are also expected in the UV-B spectral range. Further work appears necessary to determine the growth conditions that can lead to suitable concentrations of these carbon-based centers for optical experiments. Because carbon 6-rings are predicted to have a large binding energy favoring the formation of carbon clusters [35], tracking this specific defect may be crucial for understanding the synthesis of *h*-BN polytypes, in particular, the Bernal form appearing during the fabrication of *h*-BN crystals under the addition of a large amount of carbon [26,49–51]. Finally, in the context of quantum technologies, our method may stimulate follow-up studies in order to identify the carbon-based defects having an optical response in the visible and near-infrared domains and acting as single-photon emitters [56] and spin defects [57,58].

We found in *h*-BN in this study and in a previous work [32] that a strong coupling appears between the *h*-BN layers because of the Coulombic interaction between the positively polarized boron atoms and negatively polarized nitrogen atoms in neighbor *h*-BN sheets. This is clearly manifested in the PL signals of planar defects such as the 4.1 eV emitter. Beyond *h*-BN, our work opens novel perspectives for identifying point defects in materials where the stacking order could be changed, such as SiC [59], thus

providing a systematic method combining polytype control and isotope substitution, for both the host matrix and the impurities (in fact, a minimalistic approach could be to start with isotope substitution for both the host matrix and the impurities). It can be expected that the PL signals can be tuned by polytype and isotope control of the respective layers when the host material contains polarized bonds which indeed appear for heteroatomic 2D materials. Furthermore, our results may guide future theoretical and experimental studies on heterostructures of 2D materials to engineer the polarization of bonds in adjacent sheets that can tune the optical signals of planar defects in the target 2D layer.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We gratefully acknowledge C. L'Henoret and T. Cohen for their technical support at the mechanics workshop. This work was financially supported by the BONASPES project (ANR-19-CE30-0007), the ZEOLIGHT project (ANR-19-CE08-0016), and the HETERO-BNC project (ANR-20-CE09-0014-02). Support for *h*-BN crystal growth at KSU was provided by the Office of Naval Research, Award No. N00014-22-1-2582. Support for *h*-BN crystal growth at SEU was provided by the National Science Foundation of China, Grant No. 11674053. The work was partly supported by Project No. UMO-2023/51/B/ST3/02167 founded by the National Science Centre (Poland). A. G. acknowledges the support from the National Research, Development and Innovation Office of Hungary (NKFIH) in Hungary for the Quantum Information National Laboratory (Grant No. 2022-2.1.1-NL-2022-0000) and the European Union Horizon Europe project SPINUS (Grant No. 101135699). A part of the calculations was performed using the KIFÜ high-performance computation units. A. P. acknowledges the financial support of Janos Bolyai Research Fellowship of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences.

APPENDIX A: METHODS

1. *h*-BN growth by the metal flux method

Samples from SouthEast University (SEU series) were grown by using the metal flux method. For boron isotope controlled single crystal growth, high-purity iron granules (Fe, 5N purity) and chromium granules (Cr, 4N purity) were used as metal flux. Powders of ^{10}B (85 at %) or ^{11}B (99 at %) were used as source materials for the synthesis of ^{10}B -enriched *h*-BN or *h*- $^{11}\text{B}^{14}\text{N}$ crystals, respectively. For *h*- $^{\text{Nat}}\text{BN}$ crystal growth, iron (Fe, 5N purity), nickel (Ni, 6N purity), chromium (Cr, 4N purity), and cobalt (Co, 5N purity) were used as metal flux (with relative proportions detailed in Ref. [38]), with high-purity *h*- $^{\text{Nat}}\text{BN}$ powder as source materials. Carbon powder (with naturally abundant isotopes, i.e., 99% ^{12}C and 1% ^{13}C) was included in all growths to promote the *h*-BN single crystal formation [38]. Typically, the metals, boron source (^{10}B , ^{11}B , or *h*-BN powders) and carbon powder were weighted in ratios of

100:10:2, mixed together, and then loaded into an alumina crucible, which was then placed inside an alumina tube furnace. The furnace was purged 3–5 times by nitrogen gas (purity approximately 99.9%, naturally abundant isotopes) after being evacuated to a vacuum of approximately 5 Pa prior to the growth in order to minimize residue gas in the furnace tube. The temperature was then ramped to 1550 °C at rate of 6 °C/min, held at 1550 °C for 12–24 h, and then cooled slowly to 1400 °C at a rate of 4 °C/h to obtain high-quality *h*-BN crystals. Finally, the sample was cooled down to room temperature naturally. During all these processes, the flow rate of N_2 gas was kept at approximately 250 sccm.

The growth protocol at KSU is summarized in the main text.

The crystals grown at SEU and KSU have typically a lateral size of a few millimeters and a thickness of hundreds of micrometers. Given the huge value of the absorption coefficient at the band edge in *h*-BN (approximately $2 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ as estimated in Ref. [60]), PL experiments excited at wavelengths of approximately 200 nm probe the first approximately 10 nm of the *h*-BN samples. In SEU and KSU crystals with an identical nominal content of carbon, the intrinsic PL signal around 6 eV is of the same order of magnitude, thus showing comparable crystal qualities.

2. Photoluminescence spectroscopy

a. Ambient pressure measurements

The emission spectrum of the 4 eV defect was recorded by PL spectroscopy with two experimental setups devoted to macro-PL [61] and micro-PL [49], with spatial resolutions of 50 μm and 300 nm, respectively. In the two experimental configurations, the PL was excited above the *h*-BN band gap by the fourth harmonic of a cw mode-locked Ti:Sa oscillator, tunable from 193 to 205 nm with trains of 140 fs pulses at 80 MHz repetition rate and an average power of 50 μW . The samples were held on the cold finger of closed-cycle cryostats, with the possibility of temperature-dependent measurements from 8 K to room temperature (only low-temperature data are discussed in the present paper). Samples of a given series were mounted side by side in the cryostat in order to perform the PL experiments in the exact same conditions and avoid calibration issues, which could be detrimental for resolving the faint isotopic shifts of the PL lines. The detection system was composed of an $f = 500 \text{ mm}$ Czerny-Turner monochromator, equipped with an 1800 grooves mm^{-1} grating blazed at 250 nm and with a backilluminated CCD camera (Andor Newton 920), with a quantum efficiency of 50% at 210 nm.

The PL spectra of the SEU series (Sec. II) and of the $^{\text{Nat}}\text{C}:\text{h}\text{-BN}$ and $^{13}\text{C}:\text{h}\text{-BN}$ crystals (Sec. III) were acquired by macro-PL experiments, and the KSU series (Sec. II) was studied by micro-PL.

The experiments described in this section were performed at L2C, Montpellier, France.

b. Pressure-dependent measurements

Low-temperature emission spectra under continuous-wave excitation were obtained using the 275.4 nm line of a Coherent Innova 400 Ar-ion laser. The sample was mounted inside a closed-cycle helium cryostat. The spectra were dispersed by a Horiba Jobin-Yvon FHR 1000 spectrometer, and the signal was detected by a liquid nitrogen-cooled CCD camera.

High hydrostatic pressure was obtained by using a low-temperature diamond anvil cell (CryoDAC LT, easyLab Technologies Ltd). Argon was used as a pressure-transmitting medium. The diamond anvil cell was mounted in an Oxford Optistat CF cryostat equipped with a temperature controller for low-temperature measurements. Samples with a diameter of approximately 100 μm and a thickness of approximately 30 μm were loaded into the cell along with a small ruby ball. The R1-line ruby luminescence, excited by the second harmonic of an YAG:Nd laser (532 nm), was used for pressure calibration. The half width of the R1 line was also used for monitoring hydrostatic conditions in the diamond anvil cell.

The experiments described in this section were performed at PAS, Warsaw, Poland.

3. *Ab initio* calculations

The first-principles calculations were conducted using the Vienna *ab initio* simulation package code [62,63] based on projector augmented wave potentials [64,65]. The cutoff energy for the plane-wave expansion of the wave function was set to 450 eV. To prevent defect-defect interactions, a 9×9 bilayer *h*-BN supercell model was utilized with single Γ -point sampling. The interlayer van der Waals interaction was accounted for using the DFT-D3 method developed by Grimme [66].

For better comparison with experimental data, the lattice was optimized using the generalized gradient approximation of Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof [67] followed by electronic property calculations using the hybrid density functional of Heyd, Scuseria, and Ernzerhof [68]. The exchange contribution was modified to $\alpha = 0.32$ to reproduce the experimental optical gap around 6 eV. Excited state calculations were performed using the Δ SCF method [69]. We applied a von Barth correction for the total energy of the excited state [30]. A convergence threshold of 0.01 eV \AA^{-1} was set in the force calculations.

In our computational analysis, we use Huang-Rhys (HR) theory [70] to determine the photoluminescence spectrum of defects. This involves calculating the adiabatic potential energy surface for the electronic excited state and identifying phonons that contribute to optical transitions. The electronic excited state is obtained via the Δ SCF method,

assuming the transition dipole moment $\vec{\mu}_{eg}$ has no dependence on defect geometry in accordance with the Franck-Condon approximation.

The phonon sideband of the fluorescence spectrum is expressed as [71]

$$I(\hbar\omega) = \frac{n_D \omega^3}{3\epsilon_0 \pi c^3 \hbar} |\vec{\mu}_{eg}|^2 \times \sum_m |\langle \chi_{gm} | \chi_{e0} \rangle|^2 \delta(E_{ZPL} - E_{gm} - \hbar\omega), \quad (\text{A1})$$

where E_{ZPL} is the zero-phonon line energy, n_D is the material's refractive index at the ZPL energy, χ_{gm} and χ_{e0} are the vibrational levels of the ground and excited states, respectively, and E_{gm} is the energy of the electronic ground state but with m excited vibrational modes.

To compare our results with experimental data, we define the normalized luminescence intensity as

$$L(\hbar\omega) = CA(\hbar\omega), \quad (\text{A2})$$

where

$$A(\hbar\omega) = \sum_m |\langle \chi_{gm} | \chi_{e0} \rangle|^2 \delta(E_{ZPL} - E_{gm} - \hbar\omega) \quad (\text{A3})$$

and C is the normalization constant defined by $C^{-1} = \int A(\hbar\omega) \omega^3 d(\hbar\omega)$. We assume that the normal modes influencing luminescence remain unchanged upon excitation, allowing us to express $A(\hbar\omega)$ as the Fourier transform of the generating function $G(t)$ [72]:

$$A(E_{ZPL} - \hbar\omega) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G(t) e^{i\omega t - \gamma|t|} dt, \quad (\text{A4})$$

with the generating function defined as $G(t) = e^{[S(t) - S(0)]}$, where

$$S(t) = \int_0^{\infty} S(\hbar\omega) e^{-i\omega t} d(\hbar\omega). \quad (\text{A5})$$

Here, $S(\hbar\omega)$ is given by

$$S(\hbar\omega) = \sum_k S_k \delta(\hbar\omega - \hbar\omega_k), \quad (\text{A6})$$

where $S_k = (1/2\hbar)\omega_k q_k^2$ is a partial HR factor, while (q_k) represents the mass-weighted difference in geometries of the ground and excited states:

$$q_k = \frac{1}{\omega_k^2} \sum_{\alpha i} \frac{1}{m_{\alpha}^{1/2}} (F_{e,\alpha i} - F_{g,\alpha i}) \Delta r_{k,\alpha i}, \quad (\text{A7})$$

where Δr is the atomic displacement. Here, $F_{e,\alpha i} - F_{g,\alpha i}$ describes geometric changes for atom α along direction i ,

and q_k is critical for determining the phonon sideband in the photoluminescence spectrum. The total HR factor for a given optical transition is defined as $S = \sum_k S_k$.

In our calculations, linewidth broadening was incorporated by applying a Gaussian function to each mode, resulting in an additional smearing of approximately 1 meV per peak. We also assessed the impact of inhomogeneous broadening stemming from the significant presence of both isotopes, ^{10}B and ^{11}B , in $h\text{-}^{\text{Nat}}\text{BN}$ (19% and 81%, respectively). To this end, we averaged over 20 random spatial configurations for both ^{12}C and ^{13}C . In neither case did the peak position deviate by more than 0.4 meV from the mean value. Notably, the spectra obtained from averaging over different spatial configurations closely resembled those derived from averaging over the boron mass, set at 10.81 amu.

The effects of isotope composition on the zero-phonon line and sideband were considered by adjusting the phonon modes. To alleviate the computational burden of phonon calculations for different compositions, the following procedure was implemented. Initially, (squares of) phonon frequencies (F) and dynamic matrix (DM) were obtained for defects in $h\text{-BN}$ of natural abundance. The mass-scaled Hessian matrix (H) was then computed as $H = DM \times F \times DM^{-1}$, and the elements were rescaled with the masses of interest to calculate new phonon modes and frequencies for the specific composition. This approach yielded numerically equivalent photoluminescence spectra as direct calculations.

4. Growth of $h\text{-BN}$ from lithium-modified ammonia borane

The experiments described in this section were performed at IRCER, Limoges, France.

a. Synthesis of lithium-modified ammonia borane

All chemical products were stored and handled in an argon-filled glove box (Jacomex, Campus-type; O_2 and H_2O concentrations kept at ≤ 0.1 pp m and ≤ 0.8 pp m, respectively). The cleaned ball milling reactor and crucibles were stored in an oven at 100°C overnight before being introduced in the glove box to be used. Lithium amide LiNH_2 (95%) and ammonia borane complex NH_3BH_3 (97%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received.

Li-modified ammonia borane was synthesized by solid-state reaction. For a fixed molar ratio $n_{\text{NH}_3\text{BH}_3}/n_{\text{Li}}$ of 3, approximately 802 mg of NH_3BH_3 and 198 mg of LiNH_2 were placed in a stainless-steel ball-milling reactor, in the glove box. Six stainless-steel beads of 10 mm in diameter were placed on top of the powders before closing the reactor. The products were then ball milled on a pulverisette 7 premium line apparatus from Fritsch with the following parameters: five cycles of 1 min runs followed by 2 min pause (very slow rotation) at 250 revolutions per minute (rpm), reverse mode enabled and venting between each

cycle. Evacuation of excess pressure coming from the reaction between LiNH_2 and NH_3BH_3 (mainly NH_3 and H_2) was performed via a valve of the ball-milling reactor. This reaction leads to the formation of a very viscous white and opaque liquid which solidified after 2 or 3 days. The ball-milling reactor was left open in the glove box until the white powder formed and could be easily retrieved.

b. Thermochemical conversion of the lithium-modified ammonia borane precursor

The BN crucible containing the powder was introduced into a silica tube inserted in a horizontal furnace (Thermconcept ROS 50/450/12) under argon flow. The tube was then evacuated to 0.1 mbar and kept under dynamic vacuum for 30 min. Afterward, the silica tube was refilled with purified anhydrous ammonia (99.99%) to atmospheric pressure. The heating program went as follows: heating to 1000°C at a speed of $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, dwelling for 2 h, and cooling down to room temperature at $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. A constant flow of 120 mL/min passed through the silica tube during the pyrolysis. The flowing gas was switched to N_2 after the 2 h dwelling at 1000°C until the end of the treatment. Then an annealing treatment up to 1800°C was done in a graphite furnace (VHT-GR, Nabertherm) still using a BN crucible.

APPENDIX B: ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

1. Photoluminescence experiments

a. $AB\text{-}h\text{-BN}$ powder

The AB stacking of $h\text{-BN}$ synthesized from a lithium-modified ammonia borane precursor was evidenced by PL spectroscopy in the UV-C and UV-B spectral domains (Fig. 12), where the simultaneous observation of a line at approximately 6.035 eV and a ZPL doublet for the 4 eV defect proves the Bernal form of BN [26,49]. In Ref. [49], spatially resolved experiments in AA' - and AB -stacked

FIG. 12. Photoluminescence spectra of the $AB\text{-}h\text{-BN}$ powder synthesized by thermoconversion of a lithium-modified ammonia borane precursor: detection in the UV-B (a) and UV-C (b) spectral ranges. Ambient pressure, sample temperature = 8 K, PL excitation energy = 6.32 eV.

FIG. 13. Photoluminescence spectra of the AB - h -BN powder at hydrostatic pressures of 0.46 (a) and 4.76 GPa (b): experimental data (symbols) and two Gaussian-fit (solid line).

h -BN crystals demonstrated a one-to-one correlation between inversion symmetry breaking probed by second harmonic generation and the detection of an intense PL line at approximately 6.035 eV, i.e., the specific signature of the noncentrosymmetric Bernal stacking.

The pressure-dependent energies of the two ZPLs of the 4 eV defect in AB -stacked h -BN were estimated by a two-Gaussian fit (Fig. 13), allowing a quantitative analysis of the $AB1$ component (high-energy line at approximately 4.161 eV for ambient pressure) at hydrostatic pressures up to 4.76 GPa.

b. AB - h -BN microcrystals

The polytypic nature of the currently available h -BN samples synthesized by the metal flux growth method [26,49] reduces the size of AB -stacked h -BN crystals to few

FIG. 14. Pressure-induced redshifts of the ZPL doublet and phonon replica of the $AB2$ -ZPL in AB -stacked h -BN microcrystals: experimental data (symbols), replicated fit to the data in the AB - h -BN powder from Fig. 9 (dotted lines).

tens of micrometers, i.e., a dimension hardly appropriate for high-pressure measurements in a diamond-anvil cell, with limited spatial resolution compared to confocal microscopy at ambient pressure [22,26]. Nevertheless, experiments could be performed in a few samples, leading to results identical to the measurements performed in the AB -stacked h -BN powder (dotted lines in Fig. 14) within experimental error.

2. *Ab initio* calculations

The partial HR factors depicted in Fig. 15 elucidate the contributions of each normal mode to the PL spectra of the C2 and SW defects. For the C2 defect, the PL spectra in h - Nat BN are predominantly influenced by the approximately 200 meV mode, accompanied by contributions

FIG. 15. Partial HR factors for each vibration mode, calculated for the C2 and SW defects in the AA' stacking sequences of h - Nat BN. The red arrows show the atomic contributions to the leading mode at approximately 200 meV. Insets are enlargements displaying the HR factors below 120 meV.

FIG. 16. Calculated isotopic shifts of the energy splitting Δ between the zero-phonon line at approximately 4.1 eV and the phonon replica (as defined in Fig. 2) for the carbon defects, compared with the experimental values. The isotopic variations of the Δ splitting are calculated with an accuracy of approximately 1 meV.

from two additional modes near approximately 190 meV. In turn, in the case of the SW defect, the approximately 200 meV mode remains the most active; however, the contributions from modes around approximately 150 meV introduce significant discrepancies in the spectrum compared to experimental observations. Additionally, Fig. 15 illustrates the atomic contributions to the phonon eigenvectors, represented as vectors where their size indicates the extent of each atom's involvement in the vibration. Note that the total length of each normal mode is normalized to unity. For the C2 defect, the modes are largely localized at the two carbon atoms, whereas for the SW defect, a notable contribution from the host atoms is also evident.

The calculated isotopic Δ -shifts for the carbon defects are shown in Fig. 16, revealing the best agreement with experimental data for the C2 defect. Furthermore, in Fig. 17(a), we plot the Huang-Rhys factors for both carbon isotopes within the C2 defect as a function of phonon energy. Notably, we observe a decrease of 6 meV in the energy of the main mode due to ^{13}C substitution, a trend that is corroborated by our experimental results. Moreover, the ^{13}C substitution also alters the relative intensities of the three leading modes of the C2 defect, thereby modulating the PL spectrum in agreement with our experimental findings. Figure 17 further demonstrates the atomic contributions to these three modes, indicating that the two modes near approximately 190 meV are also stretching modes of carbon, albeit mixed with bulk modes to varying degrees. This mixing leads to partial delocalization and results in a redshift of their energies. Similarly, the

FIG. 17. Partial HR factors for each vibration mode, calculated (a) for the ^{12}C and ^{13}C defects in the AA' stacking sequence of $h\text{-}^{12}\text{C}$ BN and (b) for the ^{12}C defect in $h\text{-}^{10}\text{B}^{14}\text{N}$ and $h\text{-}^{11}\text{B}^{15}\text{N}$. The red arrows show the atomic contributions to the three leading modes, contributing to the phonon replica. Insets are enlargements displaying the HR factors below 120 meV.

contributions of the two additional modes also change with boron and nitrogen isotopes, as depicted in Fig. 17(b), ultimately yielding sharper signals for heavier atoms, as observed in our measurements. Additionally, Fig. 18 presents a comparison of the calculated spectra for $^{13}\text{C}4$ and $^{13}\text{C}6$ with our experimental PL measurements. It reveals greater discrepancies than those observed for the $^{13}\text{C}2$ data, as discussed in the main text.

Finally, Table II presents the impact of hydrostatic pressure on the electronic properties of the C2 defect.

FIG. 18. Simulated impact of the isotopic substitution (^{12}C vs ^{13}C) on the PL spectra of the C4 (a) and C6 (b) defects in $h\text{-}^{10}\text{B}_3\text{N}_2$. The experimental results are from Fig. 6. Unlike the calculations performed for the carbon dimer (C2) displayed in Fig. 6, and because of the theoretical accuracy of approximately 100 meV for the absolute values of the ZPL energy from one defect to another, the calculated ZPL energies of the C4 and C6 defects do not coincide with the experimental ones so that a spectral shift is applied for the comparison.

While the band gap decreases due to pressure, it also significantly shifts the positions of the Kohn-Sham levels. The most substantial shift occurs in the AA' stacking sequence, primarily attributed to changes in the energy of the empty defect level. Notably, the defects in the $AB1$ and $AB2$ configurations exhibit a less pronounced response. The calculated alterations in defect levels correspond closely with the observed variations in ZPL energies. Detailed structural modifications resulting from applied pressure are summarized in Table III. In both the AA' and

$AB1$ configurations, bond lengths and angles consistently change upon application of 10 GPa of pressure. In contrast, the $AB2$ configuration reveals a significant sliding of the defect within the symmetry plane, characterized by a marked decrease in the N-C-N angle. This structural change results in a large increase in the HR factor, which is also consistent with our experimental observations.

TABLE II. Electronic properties of C2 defect in the ground state in different stacking sequences at 0 and 10 GPa. The energy levels given in eV are aligned to the valence band maximum of each configuration. CBM is the conduction band minimum. ΔE is the difference between the energies of occupied and empty defect levels. $\Delta\Delta E$ is an electronic contribution to the pressure coefficient. Uncertainties are in the meV range.

	AA'	$AB1$	$AB2$
0 GPa			
CBM	6.09	6.11	6.12
Empty	5.62	5.55	5.65
Occupied	0.72	0.59	0.70
ΔE	4.90	4.96	4.95
10 GPa			
CBM	5.99	5.97	5.98
Empty	5.49	5.45	5.70
Occupied	0.75	0.57	0.81
ΔE	4.74	4.88	4.89
$\Delta\Delta E$	0.16	0.08	0.06

TABLE III. Relevant structural parameters computed for the C2 defect in the ground (gs) and excited (ex) states in different stacking sequences at 0 and 10 GPa. The angles are defined between the respective nearest atoms in the adjoined layers. HR is for Huang-Rhys factors.

	AA'	$AB1$	$AB2$
0 GPa			
C-C bond gs (\AA)	1.367	1.371	1.360
N-C-N gs (deg)	179.78	...	179.75
B-C-B gs (deg)	177.33	177.32	...
C-C bond ex (\AA)	1.472	1.470	1.461
N-C-N ex (deg)	177.33	...	177.08
B-C-B ex (deg)	178.04	178.02	...
HR factor	2.09	2.15	2.31
10 GPa			
C-C bond gs (\AA)	1.356	1.364	1.349
N-C-N gs (deg)	179.23	...	179.20
B-C-B gs (deg)	177.33	177.17	...
C-C bond ex (\AA)	1.458	1.452	1.451
N-C-N ex (deg)	176.08	...	174.77
B-C-B ex (deg)	176.70	176.90	...
HR factor	2.53	2.11	3.60

- [1] G. Wolfowicz, F. J. Heremans, C. P. Anderson, S. Kanai, H. Seo, A. Gali, G. Galli, and D. D. Awschalom, *Quantum guidelines for solid-state spin defects*, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **6**, 906 (2021).
- [2] G. Davies, *The optical properties of luminescence centres in silicon*, *Phys. Rep.* **176**, 83 (1989).
- [3] P. Udvarhelyi, B. Somogyi, G. Thiering, and A. Gali, *Identification of a telecom wavelength single photon emitter in silicon*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **127**, 196402 (2021).
- [4] Y. Baron, A. Durand, P. Udvarhelyi, T. Herzig, M. Khoury, S. Pezzagna, J. Meijer, I. Robert-Philip, M. Abbarchi, J.-M. Hartmann, V. Mazzocchi, J.-M. Gérard, A. Gali, V. Jacques, G. Cassabois, and A. Dréau, *Detection of single WCenters in silicon*, *ACS Photonics* **9**, 2337 (2022).
- [5] P. T. Araujo, M. Terrones, and M. S. Dresselhaus, *Defects and impurities in graphene-like materials*, *Mater. Today* **15**, 98 (2012).
- [6] D. Wong, J. Velasco, Jr., L. Ju, J. Lee, S. Kahn, H.-Z. Tsai, C. Germany, T. Taniguchi, K. Watanabe, A. Zettl, F. Wang, and M. F. Crommie, *Characterization and manipulation of individual defects in insulating hexagonal boron nitride using scanning tunnelling microscopy*, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **10**, 949 (2015).
- [7] M. Turunen, M. Brotons-Gisbert, Y. Dai, Y. Wang, E. Scerri, C. Bonato, K. D. Jöns, Z. Sun, and B. D. Gerardot, *Quantum photonics with layered 2D materials*, *Nat. Rev. Phys.* **4**, 219 (2022).
- [8] Y.-C. Lin *et al.*, *Recent advances in 2D material theory, synthesis, properties, and applications*, *ACS Nano* **17**, 9694 (2023).
- [9] Á. Gali, *Recent advances in the ab initio theory of solid-state defect qubits*, *Nanophotonics* **12**, 359 (2023).
- [10] M. Cardona and M. L. W. Thewalt, *Isotope effects on the optical spectra of semiconductors*, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **77**, 1173 (2005).
- [11] A. K. Geim and I. V. Grigorieva, *Van der Waals heterostructures*, *Nature (London)* **499**, 419 (2013).
- [12] K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, and H. Kanda, *Direct-bandgap properties and evidence for ultraviolet lasing of hexagonal boron nitride single crystal*, *Nat. Mater.* **3**, 404 (2004).
- [13] A. Katzir, J. T. Suss, A. Zunger, and A. Halperin, *Point defects in hexagonal boron nitride. I. EPR, thermoluminescence, and thermally-stimulated-current measurements*, *Phys. Rev. B* **11**, 2370 (1975).
- [14] T. Kuzuba, K. Era, T. Ishii, T. Sato, and M. Iwata, *Electron-phonon interactions in layered hexagonal boron nitride*, *Physica (Amsterdam)* **105B+C**, 339 (1981).
- [15] T. Taniguchi and K. Watanabe, *Synthesis of high-purity boron nitride single crystals under high pressure by using Ba-BN solvent*, *J. Cryst. Growth* **303**, 525 (2007).
- [16] L. Museur, E. Feldbach, and A. Kanaev, *Defect-related photoluminescence of hexagonal boron nitride*, *Phys. Rev. B* **78**, 155204 (2008).
- [17] X. Z. Du, J. Li, J. Y. Lin, and H. X. Jiang, *The origin of deep-level impurity transitions in hexagonal boron nitride*, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **106**, 021110 (2015).
- [18] R. Bourrellier, S. Meuret, A. Tararan, O. Stéphan, M. Kociak, L. H. G. Tizei, and A. Zobelli, *Bright UV single photon emission at point defects in hBN*, *Nano Lett.* **16**, 4317 (2016).
- [19] T. Q. P. Vuong, G. Cassabois, P. Valvin, A. Ouerghi, Y. Chassagneux, C. Voisin, and B. Gil, *Phonon-photon mapping in a color center in hexagonal boron nitride*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **117**, 097402 (2016).
- [20] E. Tsushima, T. Tsujimura, and T. Uchino, *Enhancement of the deep-level emission and its chemical origin in hexagonal boron nitride*, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **113**, 031903 (2018).
- [21] S. Chichibu, Y. Ishikawa, H. Kominami, and K. Hara, *Nearly temperature-independent ultraviolet light emission intensity of indirect excitons in hexagonal BN microcrystals*, *J. Appl. Phys.* **123**, 065104 (2018).
- [22] T. Pelini, C. Elias, R. Page, L. Xue, S. Liu, J. Li, J. H. Edgar, A. Dréau, V. Jacques, P. Valvin, B. Gil, and G. Cassabois, *Shallow and deep levels in carbon-doped hexagonal boron nitride crystals*, *Phys. Rev. Mater.* **3**, 094001 (2019).
- [23] K. Koronski, A. Kaminska, N. D. Zhigadlo, C. Elias, G. Cassabois, and B. Gil, *Spontaneous emission of color centers at 4 eV in hexagonal boron nitride under hydrostatic pressure*, *Superlattices Microstruct.* **131**, 1 (2019).
- [24] A. S. Vokhmintsev, I. A. Weinstein, and D. Zamyatin, *Electron-phonon interactions in subband excited photoluminescence of hexagonal boron nitride*, *J. Lumin.* **208**, 363 (2019).
- [25] A. S. Vokhmintsev, I. A. Weinstein, M. G. Minin, and S. A. Shalyakin, *Thermally stimulated processes in the luminescence of carbon-related defects for h-BN micropowder*, *Radiation Measurements* **124**, 35 (2019).
- [26] A. Rousseau, P. Valvin, C. Elias, L. Xue, J. Li, J. H. Edgar, B. Gil, and G. Cassabois, *Stacking-dependent deep level emission in boron nitride*, *Phys. Rev. Mater.* **6**, 094009 (2022).
- [27] K. P. Korona, J. Binder, A. K. Dabrowska, J. Iwanski, A. Reszka, T. Korona, M. Tokarczyk, R. Stepniewski, and A. Wysmolek, *Growth temperature induced changes of luminescence in epitaxial BN: From colour centres to donor-acceptor recombination*, *Nanoscale* **15**, 9864 (2023).
- [28] C. Attacalite, M. Bockstedte, A. Marini, A. Rubio, and L. Wirtz, *Coupling of excitons and defect states in boron-nitride nanostructures*, *Phys. Rev. B* **83**, 144115 (2011).
- [29] L. Weston, D. Wickramaratne, M. Mackoite, A. Alkauskas, and C. G. Van de Walle, *Native point defects and impurities in hexagonal boron nitride*, *Phys. Rev. B* **97**, 214104 (2018).
- [30] M. Mackoite-Sinkevičienė, M. Maciaszek, C. Van de Walle, and A. Alkauskas, *Carbon dimer defect as a source of the 4.1 eV luminescence in hexagonal boron nitride*, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **115**, 212101 (2019).
- [31] T. Korona and M. Chojecki, *Exploring point defects in hexagonal boron-nitrogen monolayers*, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.* **119**, e25925 (2019).
- [32] S. Li, A. Pershin, P. Li, and A. Gali, *Exceptionally strong coupling of defect emission in hexagonal boron nitride to stacking sequences*, *npj 2D Mater. Appl.* **8**, 16 (2024).
- [33] H. Hamdi, G. Thiering, Z. Bodrog, V. Ivády, and A. Gali, *Stone-Wales defects in hexagonal boron nitride as ultraviolet emitters*, *npj Comput. Mater.* **6**, 178 (2020).
- [34] M. Winter, M. H. E. Bousquet, D. Jacquemin, I. Duchemin, and X. Blase, *Photoluminescent properties of the carbon-dimer defect in hexagonal boron-nitride: A many-body*

- finite-size cluster approach*, *Phys. Rev. Mater.* **5**, 095201 (2021).
- [35] S. Li, A. Pershin, G. Thiering, P. Udvarhelyi, and A. Gali, *Ultraviolet quantum emitters in hexagonal boron nitride from carbon clusters*, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **13**, 3150 (2022).
- [36] A. Kirchhoff, T. Deilmann, and M. Rohlfing, *Excited-state geometry relaxation of point defects in monolayer hexagonal boron nitride*, *Phys. Rev. B* **109**, 085127 (2024).
- [37] M. Maciaszek, L. Razinkovas, and A. Alkauskas, *Thermodynamics of carbon point defects in hexagonal boron nitride*, *Phys. Rev. Mater.* **6**, 014005 (2022).
- [38] S.-Y. Zhang, K. Xu, X.-K. Zhao, Z.-Y. Shao, and N. Wan, *Improved hBN single-crystal growth by adding carbon in the metal flux*, *Cryst. Growth Des.* **19**, 6252 (2019).
- [39] R. Cuscó, J. H. Edgar, S. Liu, J. Li, and L. Artús, *Isotopic disorder: The prevailing mechanism in limiting the phonon lifetime in hexagonal BN*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **124**, 167402 (2020).
- [40] T. Q. P. Vuong, S. Liu, A. Van der Lee, R. Cuscó, L. Artús, T. Michel, P. Valvin, J. H. Edgar, G. Cassabois, and B. Gil, *Isotope engineering of van der Waals interactions in hexagonal boron nitride*, *Nat. Mater.* **17**, 152 (2018).
- [41] E. Janzen, H. Schutte, J. Plo, A. Rousseau, T. Michel, W. Desrat, P. Valvin, V. Jacques, G. Cassabois, B. Gil, and J. Edgar, *Boron and nitrogen isotope effects on hexagonal boron nitride properties*, *Adv. Mater.* **36**, 2306033 (2024).
- [42] R. Cuscó, B. Gil, G. Cassabois, and L. Artús, *Temperature dependence of Raman-active phonons and anharmonic interactions in layered hexagonal BN*, *Phys. Rev. B* **94**, 155435 (2016).
- [43] A. J. Giles, S. Dai, I. Vurgaftman, T. Hoffman, S. Liu, L. Lindsay, C. T. Ellis, N. Assefa, I. Chatzakis, T. L. Reinecke, J. G. Tischler, M. M. Fogler, J. H. Edgar, D. N. Basov, and J. D. Caldwell, *Ultralow-loss polaritons in isotopically pure boron nitride*, *Nat. Mater.* **17**, 134 (2018).
- [44] M. Maciaszek and L. Razinkovas, *Blue quantum emitter in hexagonal boron nitride and a carbon chain tetramer: A first-principles study*, *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* **7**, 18979 (2024).
- [45] D. G. Thomas and J. J. Hopfield, *Isoelectronic traps due to nitrogen in gallium phosphide*, *Phys. Rev.* **150**, 680 (1966).
- [46] G. Davies, E. C. Lightowers, and M. do Carmo, *Carbon-related vibronic bands in electron-irradiated silicon*, *J. Phys. C* **16**, 5503 (1983).
- [47] B. Gil, W. Desrat, A. Rousseau, C. Elias, P. Valvin, M. Moret, J. Li, E. Janzen, J. H. Edgar, and G. Cassabois, *Polytypes of sp²-bonded boron nitride*, *Crystals* **12**, 782 (2022).
- [48] R. S. Pease, *An x-ray study of boron nitride*, *Acta Crystallogr.* **5**, 356 (1952).
- [49] A. Rousseau, P. Valvin, W. Desrat, L. Xue, J. Li, J. H. Edgar, G. Cassabois, and B. Gil, *Bernal boron nitride crystals identified by deep-ultraviolet cryomicroscopy*, *ACS Nano* **16**, 2756 (2022).
- [50] A. Rousseau, M. Moret, P. Valvin, W. Desrat, J. Li, E. Janzen, L. Xue, J. H. Edgar, G. Cassabois, and B. Gil, *Determination of the optical bandgap of the Bernal and rhombohedral boron nitride polymorphs*, *Phys. Rev. Mater.* **5**, 064602 (2021).
- [51] A. Rousseau, P. Valvin, L. Xue, J. Li, J. H. Edgar, B. Gil, and G. Cassabois, *Phonon-assisted broadening in Bernal boron nitride: A comparison between indirect and direct excitons*, *Phys. Rev. B* **106**, 035203 (2022).
- [52] H. X. Jiang and J. Y. Lin, *Hexagonal boron nitride for deep ultraviolet photonic devices*, *Semicond. Sci. Technol.* **29**, 084003 (2014).
- [53] A. Mballo, A. Srivastava, S. Sundaram, P. Vuong, S. Karrakchou, Y. Halfaya, S. Gautier, P. L. Voss, A. Ahaitouf, J.-P. Salvestrini, and A. Ougazzaden, *Towards P-type conduction in hexagonal boron nitride: Doping study and electrical measurements analysis of hBN/AlGaN heterojunctions*, *Nanomater. Nanotechnol.* **11**, 211 (2021).
- [54] S. Lu, P. Shen, H. Zhang, G. Liu, B. Guo, Y. Cai, H. Chen, F. Xu, T. Zheng, F. Xu, X. Chen, D. Cai, and J. Kang, *Towards n-type conductivity in hexagonal boron nitride*, *Nat. Commun.* **13**, 3109 (2022).
- [55] A. Perepeliuc, R. Gujrati, A. Srivastava, P. Vuong, V. Ottapilakkal, P. L. Voss, S. Sundaram, J. P. Salvestrini, and A. Ougazzaden, *Photoinduced doping in hexagonal boron nitride*, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **122**, 263503 (2023).
- [56] N. Mendelson, D. Chugh, J. R. Reimers, T. S. Cheng, A. Gottscholl, H. Long, C. J. Mellor, A. Zettl, V. Dyakonov, P. H. Beton, S. V. Novikov, C. Jagadish, H. Hoe Tan, M. J. Ford, M. Toth, C. Bradac, and I. Aharonovich, *Identifying carbon as the source of visible single-photon emission from hexagonal boron nitride*, *Nat. Mater.* **20**, 321 (2021).
- [57] N. Chejanovsky, A. Mukherjee, J. Geng, Y.-C. Chen, Y. Kim, A. Denisenko, A. Finkler, T. Taniguchi, K. Watanabe, D. Bhaktavatsala Rao Dasari, P. Auburger, A. Gali, J. H. Smet, and J. Wrachtrup, *Single-spin resonance in a van der Waals embedded paramagnetic defect*, *Nat. Mater.* **20**, 1079 (2021).
- [58] H. L. Stern, Q. Gu, J. Jarman, S. Eizagirre Barker, N. Mendelson, D. Chugh, S. Schott, H. H. Tan, H. Sirringhaus, I. Aharonovich, and M. Atatüre, *Room-temperature optically detected magnetic resonance of single defects in hexagonal boron nitride*, *Nat. Commun.* **13**, 618 (2022).
- [59] A. L. Falk, B. B. Buckley, G. Calusine, W. F. Koehl, V. V. Dobrovitski, A. Politi, C. A. Zorman, P. X.-L. Feng, and D. D. Awschalom, *Polytype control of spin qubits in silicon carbide*, *Nat. Commun.* **4**, 1819 (2013).
- [60] C. Elias, G. Fugallo, P. Valvin, C. L'Henoret, J. Li, J. H. Edgar, F. Sottile, M. Lazzeri, A. Ouerghi, B. Gil, and G. Cassabois, *Flat bands and giant light-matter interaction in hexagonal boron nitride*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **127**, 137401 (2021).
- [61] C. Elias, P. Valvin, T. Pelini, A. Summerfield, C. J. Mellor, T. S. Cheng, L. Eaves, C. T. Foxon, P. H. Beton, S. V. Novikov, B. Gil, and G. Cassabois, *Direct band-gap crossover in epitaxial monolayer boron nitride*, *Nat. Commun.* **10**, 2639 (2019).
- [62] G. Kresse and J. Furthmüller, *Efficiency of ab-initio total energy calculations for metals and semiconductors using a plane-wave basis set*, *Comput. Mater. Sci.* **6**, 15 (1996).
- [63] G. Kresse and J. Furthmüller, *Efficient iterative schemes for ab initio total-energy calculations using a plane-wave basis set*, *Phys. Rev. B* **54**, 11169 (1996).

- [64] P. Blöchl, *Projector augmented-wave method*, *Phys. Rev. B* **50**, 17953 (1994).
- [65] G. Kresse and D. Joubert, *From ultrasoft pseudopotentials to the projector augmented-wave method*, *Phys. Rev. B* **59**, 1758 (1999).
- [66] S. Grimme, J. Antony, S. Ehrlich, and H. Krieg, *A consistent and accurate ab initio parametrization of density functional dispersion correction (DFT-D) for the 94 elements H – Pu*, *J. Chem. Phys.* **132**, 154104 (2010).
- [67] J. P. Perdew, K. Burke, and M. Ernzerhof, *Generalized gradient approximation made simple*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **77**, 3865 (1996).
- [68] J. Heyd, G. Scuseria, and M. Ernzerhof, *Hybrid functionals based on a screened Coulomb potential*, *J. Chem. Phys.* **118**, 8207 (2003).
- [69] A. Gali, E. Janzén, P. Deák, G. Kresse, and E. Kaxiras, *Theory of spin-conserving excitation of the NV-center in diamond*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **103**, 186404 (2009).
- [70] K. Huang and A. Rhys, *Theory of light absorption and non-radiative transitions in F-centres*, *Proc. R. Soc. A* **204**, 406 (1950).
- [71] A. Stoneham, *Theory of Defects in Solids: Electronic Structure of Defects in Insulators and Semiconductors* (Oxford University, New York, 2001).
- [72] A. Alkauskas, B. B. Buckley, D. D. Awschalom, and C. G. Van de Walle, *First-principles theory of the luminescence lineshape for the triplet transition in diamond NV centres*, *New J. Phys.* **16**, 073026 (2014).